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Printed Materials (release 2) D6.7

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1.0	31/03/2020	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti Raffaella Santucci	QED, QED	Final version

Statement of originality:

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a short overview of the production of all print and presentation materials that have been or will be used for the communication and dissemination of Q-SORT. It follows *Q-SORT D6.2-D6.3 Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan including graphic design guidelines (releases 1-2)*, *Q-SORT D6.1-D6.5 Project Website and Logo (release 1-2)*, and *Q-SORT D6.6 - Printed Materials (release 1)*. All future printed materials for Q-SORT will be based on the designs and templates described in this document. Printed materials play a key role in dissemination and communication, as the first impression one gets of the project, which cannot be undone, is imparted by them.

This document comprises four chapters.

Chapter 1 is a short introduction.

Chapter 2 provides a brief overview of the philosophy that was followed in designing the dissemination materials.

Chapter 3 provides a list of the graphics assets produced for the first release (*Q-SORT D6.6 - Printed Materials*) and a description of the design process.

Chapter 4 provides a **list of the graphics assets produced since the first release** and sums up the conclusions and take-home messages that were gleaned through this work.

Chapter 5 provides low-resolution copies and photos of the designs.

1 INTRODUCTION - WHO WILL BE USING THESE DESIGNS?

Within Q-SORT the dissemination and communication materials are tools that will be used by:

- All partners
- All WP leaders
- Particularly by the staff responsible for each institution's communication activities.

In addition, as this is a public document and is available on the project's website, it will be accessible by external parties interested in disseminating and communicating Q-SORT.

This deliverable will be updated periodically at a later phase of the project according to the project's needs.

2 DESIGN PHILOSOPHY

The design of the printed materials was based on two simple but effective requirements: we aimed to define a graphic identity that is at the same time distinctive and classic. Achieving both a degree of timelessness and a striking design that 'speaks to everyone' has in turn two significant consequences.

A timeless and classic look means that the design is conceived to 'age well'.

On the other hand, a strong graphic statement that is simple, easy to identify, and based on universal proportions (such as for instance certain mathematical ratios) allows the use of the same design/theme for both dissemination and communication. This strong visual identity was consistently 'declined' in the various print designs, as detailed in the next paragraph.

Both considerations translate into cost and labour savings for the project, especially with a view to its future upkeep/sustainability.

Another cost-saving consideration was the idea of designing templates for Brochures and Posters that the partners will be able to easily fill in and print locally as the need arises (see below).

3 DESIGNS PRODUCED FOR THE FIRST RELEASE

In terms of printed materials for dissemination and communication, the needs of such an ambitious project as Q-SORT are many. Broadly speaking, some printed assets are meant to be general-purpose, i.e. deployable anywhere, whilst others are event-specific, i.e. tailored to each specific Q-SORT International Conference. Based on the project schedule as well as on an evaluation of the overall progress so far (and in particular on DE6.3, DE6.5, and DE6.6), the following assets were thus identified and then designed (asterisk marks designs that were updated or redone for the Second Release):

1. *foldable three-sided general-purpose A4 Project Brochure;
2. *template for event-specific A2 Project Poster;
3. general-purpose 80x200 Project Vinyl Banner;
4. *template for conference-specific A4 Book of Abstracts;
5. *general-purpose Q-SORT-branded Tote Bag;
6. template for Q-SORT Slides.

1) General-purpose three-fold A4 Project Brochure, to be deployed at various events as a general presentation of the project. The choice of a standard ISO 216 / DIN format instead of more ‘fashionable’ ones translates into savings for the project and in no way diminishes the impact of the design. The standard small format also makes it easy to arrange for local and/or future additional print runs.

2) Template for event-specific vertical A2 Project Poster, printable as A3 if necessary. The same considerations as above are valid regarding ISO 216 / DIN. A2 was chosen as the largest possible format that can be hung without too much trouble on pinboards and in public spaces – since, trivially, a larger format guarantees greater visibility. The design is compatible with printing in A3, which is significantly cheaper for small runs of digital prints.

3) General-purpose 80x200 standalone Vinyl Banner, to advertise and signal events taking place in a specific venue, such as conferences, seminars, lectures, press conferences, etc. The choice of PVC as the printing material makes the roll-up Banner suitable for outdoor use as well.

4) Template for the conference-specific A4 Book of Abstracts / Conference Proceedings, which has three functions:

- it provides readers with abstracts for all the topics of all the talks and all the posters presented at the conference;
- it provides a list of all participants with their contact details;
- it is also meant as a memento of the conference for all participants.

5) General-purpose Q-SORT-branded Tote Bag, to be given to all conference participants as well as to guests.

6) Template for Q-SORT slide presentations. To be used by all partners when presenting on behalf of Q-SORT. A set of coherent graphic rules is given in the template.

The new designs were initially showcased at the [First Q-SORT International Conference on Electron Beam Shaping in Space and Time](#). A first run of 1500 Brochures, 10 A2 Posters, and one Vinyl Banner was deployed on that occasion, during which it was evident that the strong, sober Q-SORT designs made the project stand out, given the generally formless and cluttered designs with which science projects and events are generally publicised. Posters and brochures that were not picked up by visitors were split between FZJ and CNR for future redeployment.

Insofar as possible, Q-SORT designs are being printed locally by partners, close to where they are meant to be deployed, in order to save on expenses and environmental impact. These designs are sent to partners with specific instructions as to the type of printing process, paper, and finish to be adopted, so as to ensure a consistently high standard of quality.

All the designs were optimised for offset printing but can be output as high-quality laser or inkjet prints if necessary.

3.1 THE ACTUAL DESIGN PROCESS

The design process started from the idea of animating the Project Logo, described in *D6.1 - Project Website and Logo (first release)* and in *D6.5 - Project Website and Logo (second release)*. We developed and explored several possibilities for the animation studies made for the logo until we reached a satisfying

version, which we used as a leitmotiv throughout. Having settled on the main graphic element and proportions, special care was taken in considering the interplay of the design with the type of paper and of printing method chosen for each of the intended formats. Then we proceeded to consistently 'decline' the leitmotiv in the various designs. For each asset we explored different combination of colours, playing with the same black/white/red palette. In the specific case of the A2 Project Poster, three versions were designed and two versions were actually issued, since the hosting partner liked to use them both.

Throughout the design phase, all the guidelines regarding the use of the various official logos were observed.

3.2 COPYWRITING

Similar considerations of simplicity and efficacy were adopted for the copywriting. The latter, insofar as possible, eschewed lingo in favour of clear and simple explanations, understandable by the general public, but also providing meaningful information for specialists. The text can be read from Figure 2 in the next chapter.

4 DESIGNS PRODUCED FOR THE SECOND RELEASE

In response to the evolving needs of the Project, the following items were designed and printed:

7. NEW foldable three-sided general-purpose A4 Project Brochure;
8. event-specific A2 Project Posters;
9. event-specific square Project Poster for Instagram/Facebook;
10. NEW conference-specific A4 Book of Abstracts (for Q-SORT Conference in Juelich and in Erlangen);
11. conference-specific Q-SORT-branded Tote Bags;
12. NEW Q-SORT Event Participation Certificate;
13. NEW Q-SORT Official Letterhead.

7) The A4 Project Brochure was redesigned for the [2019 Q-SORT International Conference On Quantum Imaging And Electron Beam Shaping](#) held in Erlangen on 2-5 July 2019 and for the EIC Pathfinder event "[Connect to the future of innovation](#)" held in Bucharest on 19-21 June 2019. The redesign had many different objectives, i.e.:

- to make the brochure more impactful and the user experience more rich;
- to further harmonise the design of the Project Brochure with that of the Book of Abstracts, since they were both included in the welcome kit given to the Q-SORT Conference attendees in Erlangen;
- to make room for an updated text in the inner fold, more concise and more reflective of the Project progress so far.

The new design is based on the hologram version of the unwrapper element of the sorter (a.k.a. "Sorter 1") for the fan-out configuration. This striking hologram was also featured in the Q-SORT Video and has become one of the leitmotifs of the Project's graphics. Unlike the black-and-white outer fold, the inner fold of the Brochure features vibrant primary colours: this chromatic strategy was chosen so as to suggest a sense of discovery and visual enrichment upon opening the Brochure.

The new Project Brochure was printed in 6500 copies, which were directly disseminated at the [2019 Q-SORT Conference](#) in Erlangen and at the EIC Pathfinder event "[Connect to the future of innovation](#)" in Bucharest, then split between the partners for further dissemination at the conferences they would attend.

8) The A2 Project Poster design was updated and event-specific Posters were offset printed from the CMYK file for the 2019 Q-SORT Conference in Erlangen. The same design was rendered as RGB with blacks optimised for additive colour synthesis and used for promoting the conference over the Web.

9) A square design for the Project Poster had to be worked out, since Instagram only displays square-cropped or square-pillared pictures. The square design in RGB form was used for announcing and promoting the first Q-SORT online Interdisciplinary Training Webinar (ITW), "How to contribute to Wikipedia". The online ITW was conceived in response to the COVID-19 pandemic and took place on 30 March 2020.

10) The Book of Abstracts (BoA) was chosen as the most practical format for providing all the necessary information to the Q-SORT Conference participants. First of all, it provides readers with abstracts for all the topics of all the talks and all the posters presented at the Q-SORT Conference, including the Science Bash, an outreach initiative aimed at engaging high-school students. Secondly, the BoA provides a list of all participants with their contact details. Thirdly, it is meant as a memento of the conference for all participants.

Two separate designs for the Book of Abstracts were made: one for the [2018 Q-SORT Conference](#) in Juelich and one for the [2019 Q-SORT Conference](#) in Erlangen. The latter was made concurrently with the A4 Project Brochure, so as to make these two complementary graphics assets work together as part of the welcome kit for attendees.

11) The Q-SORT Tote Bags are part of the welcome kit for the annual Q-SORT conference. Following the preference expressed each time by the hosting partner, the Tote Bag for the [2018 Q-SORT Conference](#) in Juelich was printed black over white canvas, while that for the [2019 Q-SORT Conference](#) in Erlangen was printed white over black canvas.

12) The new Q-SORT Event Participation Certificate was designed for all the attendees to Q-SORT Conferences or Interdisciplinary Training Webinars who have to provide proof of their participation. The Q-SORT logo was used as the basis for a very sparse typeset design. The design was made in black and white so as to be quickly printable off any standard office printer, on any type of paper.

13) The new Q-SORT Official Letterhead was designed for all official printed letters and communications pertaining to the Project. As for the Participation Certificate, a simple, sparse black-and-white design was chosen, so as to be quickly printable off any standard office printer, on any type of paper.

5 LOW-RESOLUTION COPIES OF DESIGNS

(NB: numbering follows that of the bullet points on p. 5 and p. 8)

Figure 1a: General-purpose three-fold A4 Project Brochure (outer fold)

<h2>About</h2>	<p>Q-SORT is a cutting-edge research and innovation project funded by the European Union.</p> <p>It introduces a revolutionary concept whereby the transmission electron microscope (TEM) is employed as a so-called Quantum Sorter, i.e. a device that is able to pick out and display detailed information about electron quantum states. This in turn provides researchers with precious new information about the sample being examined.</p> <p>The project -which includes applications in physics, biology, and biochemistry- is expected to have a wide-ranging impact due to the ubiquitous adoption of TEM and STEM across many disciplines. Indeed, strong interdisciplinarity, featuring a multi-year collaboration between physicists and biologists, is one of Q-SORT's defining traits. The project features a robust international consortium with potential industrial applications.</p> <p>Q-SORT also has foundational value in physics as it fosters its own kind of sparse-sensing approach to TEM, advancing the field in the direction of quantum measurement. Intuitively, sparse sensing is analogous to how we recognise familiar people from just a few small details: it means that</p>	<p>only a few measurements are taken compared to traditional approaches – yet these are still sufficient to extract all the relevant information. A similar thing happens when we recognise relatives just from their silhouette or profile or any other small detail: we don't need to see their full face to identify them.</p> <p>The project harnesses the know-how of some of the top players in the world of orbital angular momentum, quantum optics, TEM, and cryoTEM.</p> <p>The scientific coordinator and principal investigator of Q-SORT is Vincenzo Grillo, a senior research fellow at CNR -the Italian National Research Council- and the recipient of the prestigious Humboldt Foundation's Bessel Research Award for his work on beam shaping.</p> <p>Q-SORT is funded by the FET OPEN Programme of the European Commission, the executive body of the European Union - Grant Agreement no. 766970 Q-SORT.</p> <p>A policy based on equal opportunities informs the entire project.</p>		
<h2>The Q-SORT Consortium</h2>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CNR-NANO (Project Coordinator) – Italy - Forschungszentrum Jülich – Germany - FEI (Thermo Fisher Scientific) – The Netherlands - Max Planck Institut – Germany - University of Glasgow – United Kingdom - QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. – United Kingdom - Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia – Italy - Maastricht University – The Netherlands 			
<h2>Contact</h2>	<p>Project Coordinator</p> <p>Vincenzo Grillo vincenzo.grillo@cnr.it</p>	<p>Communication Manager</p> <p>Luca Marco Carlo Giberti lmcg@qedproductions.co.uk</p>	<p>Executive Manager</p> <p>Raffaella Santucci raffaella@qedproductions.co.uk</p>	<p>5% CNR-NANO</p> <p>Via Campi 213/A 41125 Modena - Italy</p>

Figure 1b: General-purpose three-fold A4 Project Brochure (inner fold)

International Conference on
Electron Beam Shaping in
Space and Time

Sunday 27 – Wednesday 30
May 2018

Zentralbibliothek - Building 04.7
Forschungszentrum Jülich
Wilhelm-Johnen-Strasse
52428 Jülich, Germany

qsort.eu

Q-SORT

Q-SORT

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 766970

Figure 2a: Conference-specific vertical Poster - white background

Figure 2b: Conference-specific vertical Poster - black background v.1

Figure 2c: Conference-specific vertical Poster - black background v.2

Figure 3a: General-purpose 80x200 stand-alone Vinyl Banner

Figure 3b: General-purpose 80x200 stand-alone Vinyl Banner

Figure 5: General-purpose Tote Bag, black version

Figure 7a: NEW general-purpose three-fold A4 Project Brochure (outer fold)

About Q-SORT:

Q-SORT is a cutting-edge research project funded by the FET OPEN Programme of the European Union.

It introduces a revolutionary concept whereby the transmission electron microscope (TEM) is employed as a so-called **Quantum Sorter**, i.e. a device capable of extracting detailed information about electron quantum states.

This in turn could provide researchers with **precious new insights on delicate samples which are normally damaged by TEM**.

The project –which includes proof-of-principle applications in physics, biology, and biochemistry– is developing this **key enabling technology** by pooling some of the top players in the world in the fields of **orbital angular momentum, quantum optics, and cryoTEM**.

Q-SORT also has foundational value in physics as it fosters its own kind of **sparse-sensing** approach to TEM, advancing the field in the direction of quantum measurement.

Q-SORT is expected to have a **wide-ranging impact** due to the ubiquitous nature of TEM.

The project features a robust international consortium, with a strong industrial partner.

Q-SORT is the brainchild of Vincenzo Grillo, a senior research fellow at CNR –the Italian National Research Council– and the recipient of the prestigious Humboldt Foundation's Bessel Research Award for his work on beam shaping.

www.qsort.eu

The Q-SORT Consortium:

- CNR-NANO Project Coordinator (Italy)
- Forschungszentrum Jülich (Germany)
- FEI, Thermo Fisher Scientific (The Netherlands)
- Max Planck Institut (Germany)
- University of Glasgow (UK)
- QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. (UK)
- Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia (Italy)
- Maastricht University (The Netherlands)

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 769970

Figure 7b: NEW general-purpose three-fold A4 Project Brochure (inner fold)

Figure 7c: NEW general-purpose three-fold A4 Project Brochures

Figure 8a: Conference-specific vertical Poster - black background 2019

Figure 8b: Event-specific vertical Poster - black background 2020

Figure 9: Event-specific square Banner - black background 2020

Figure 10a: NEW conference-specific A4 Book of Abstracts (for Q-SORT Conference in Juelich and in Erlangen)

Figure 10b: NEW conference-specific A4 Book of Abstracts (for Q-SORT Conference in Juelich)

Figure 10c: NEW conference-specific A4 Book of Abstracts (for Q-SORT Conference in Juelich)

Figure 10d: NEW conference-specific A4 Book of Abstracts (for Q-SORT Conference in Juelich)

Figure 11: Conference-specific Q-SORT-branded Tote Bags (for Q-SORT Conference in Juelich)

Figure 12a: NEW Q-SORT Event Participation Certificate

Figure 12b: NEW Q-SORT Event Participation Certificate

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41125 Modena - Italy

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is funded
by the EU

Figure 13a: NEW Q-SORT Official Letterhead

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Figure 13b: NEW Q-SORT Official Letterhead

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41125 Modena - Italy

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Figure 13c: NEW Q-SORT Official Letterhead

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Dear NAME, SURNAME

Letter of invitation

It is our pleasure to officially accept your application to participate in the [International Conference on Electron Beam Shaping in Space and Time](#) and to invite you to the conference, which will be held in [Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany between 28 and 30 May, 2018](#).

The conference is organized jointly by the partners of the projects:

[Quantum Sorter - A new Measurement Paradigm in Electron Microscopy \(H2020-FETOPEN\)](#)
[Science and Applications of Electron Wavefunctions Shaped and Manipulated by Engineered Nanoholograms \(Deutsch-Israelische Projektkooperation grant\)](#)
with the support of [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#) and [Institute Nanoscience CNR \(CNR-NANO\)](#)

It will address challenges and opportunities in electron beam shaping and its applications, showcase cutting-edge theoretical and experimental developments in the form of invited plenary talks and contributed presentations and include space for product displays. There will be opportunities for networking and discussion, as well as an edit-a-thon, an interdisciplinary workshop and a webinar.

Topics covered in the program will include:

- Coherent manipulation of electron wavefunctions by light interaction and matter.
- Studies of the foundational aspects of quantum physics and their applications to materials science.
- Ideas and methods for near-interaction-free and dose-effective imaging of matter.

Please note that we are unable to support your expenses to attend the conference.

We look forward to welcoming you in Jülich soon.

Yours sincerely,

Ady Arie, Rafal Dunin-Borkowski and Vincenzo Grillo

Q-SORT
www.qsort.eu

% CNR-NANO
Via Campi 213/A
41125 Modena - Italy

This project
is funded
by the EU

Figure 14: Q-SORT Letter of Invitation

6 CONCLUSIONS

We think the results show the benefit of involving professionals with the right profile in the design and copywriting process.

Suitable 'buffer time' needs to be scheduled between completion of the designs to the coordinator's and designers' satisfaction, and their final delivery. This is in order to take into account possible changes at the request of partners or of those institutions whose logo is included in the design. The number and duration of these 'refinement iterations' seems to grow exponentially with the number of partners involved.

Further suitable buffer time should be factored in for checking printed samples ahead of each print run: the correct rendition of text, logos, and graphics/colours should be checked, as well as the quality of the folding in the case of the brochures.

The Consortium now has general-purpose Project Brochures, Posters, stand-alone Banners, Book-of-Abstracts templates, Official Letterhead, and Tote Bags ready for any event.

Partners now have all the templates they might need to start planning the printing of their own posters and brochures.

ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL